

PREP4BLUE

METHODS AND TOOLS FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS.....	7
1 INTRODUCTION	8
1.1 MISSION “RESTORE OUR OCEAN AND WATERS”	8
1.2 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT IN THE MISSION	10
1.3 MISSION ENABLER “PUBLIC MOBILIZATION AND ENGAGEMENT”	11
1.4 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT AND PUBLIC MOBILIZATION IN PREP4BLUE: CITIZEN(S) V.S. STAKEHOLDERS(S)	12
2 CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT BY PREP4BLUE: METHODS AND RESULTS	14
2.1 ENGAGED RESEARCH AMONG CITIZENS NETWORKS	14
2.2 PRE/POST ENGAGEMENT SURVEYS	14
2.2.1 <i>Pre-engagement survey</i>	15
2.2.2 <i>Post-engagement surveys</i>	15
2.3 INTERVIEWS WITH PARTICIPANTS/REPRESENTATIVES OF AQUATIC CITIZEN SCIENCE INITIATIVES	15
2.4 CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT TRAINING WORKSHOPS	16
3 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT: PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS, METHODS IDENTIFICATION AND RESULTS	16
3.1 DESKTOP STUDY FOR STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT IN AND FOR THE MISSION	17
3.1.1 <i>Stakeholders to be involved in the Mission based on desktop study</i>	19
3.1.2 <i>Actions/Methods to involve the Stakeholders based on desktop study</i>	20
3.2 STAKEHOLDERS ADDRESSED BY PREP4BLUE	21
3.3 TO THIS END, THE DATA AND ANALYSES DEVELOPED THROUGH THE DESKTOP STUDY DESCRIBED ABOVE FED INTO THE ACTIVITIES OUTLINED IN THE FOLLOWING PARAGRAPHS. THESE ACTIVITIES FURTHER DEVELOPED THE FINDINGS INTO TOOLS AND GUIDELINES TO SUPPORT MISSION-FUNDED R&I PROJECTS, AS WELL AS INTO PILOT ACTIONS IMPLEMENTED IN COLLABORATION WITH THE OTHER CSAs. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT TOOLS	22
3.3.1 <i>Stakeholder engagement guidelines</i>	23
3.3.2 <i>WaveLinks – SH engagement method factsheet</i>	23
3.3.3 <i>Webinars</i>	26
3.3.4 <i>Helpdesk</i>	27
3.4 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT COMMUNITY OF PRACTICES	28
3.5 PILOT STAKEHOLDER ASSEMBLIES	29
3.6 CAPACITY BUILDING NEEDED FOR STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT: IDENTIFYING NECESSARY SKILLS	30
4 RECOMMENDATIONS FROM PREP4BLUE.....	32
4.1 CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT RECOMMENDATIONS	32
4.1.1 <i>Context/Issue</i>	32
4.1.2 <i>Recommendation</i>	32
4.2 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT RECOMMENDATIONS	32

4.3	COMMUNICATION RECOMMENDATIONS	34
4.3.1	<i>Mission Communication Activities</i>	34
4.3.2	<i>Marine Science Communication activities</i>	35
5	CONCLUSIONS	37

TABLE OF FIGURES

TABLE 1.	TABLE OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS USED IN PREP4BLUE AND THE DOCUMENT.....	7
TABLE 2.	ANALYSIS CRITERIA FOR STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT IN THE MISSIONS AND CLUSTER 6 WORK PROGRAMS OF 2021-2022 AND 2023-2024.	17
TABLE 3.	NUMBER OF TOPICS PER WORK PROGRAM (MISSIONS & CLUSTER 6) AND PER YEAR (2021-2022 & 2023-2024) ASKING FOR STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT	18
TABLE 4.	STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTION TYPE WITH THE REQUIRED STAKEHOLDERS	21
TABLE 5.	RECOMMENDATIONS ON STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT RELATED TO MISSION INTERNAL COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES	35
TABLE 6.	RECOMMENDATIONS ON STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT RELATED TO MARINE SCIENCE COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES	36
FIGURE 1.	MISSION OBJECTIVES AND ENABLERS (SOURCE: EUROPEAN COMMISSION)	9
FIGURE 2.	MISSION LIGHTHOUSES AND THEIR SPECIFIC OBJECTIVE IN THE FIRST PHASE OF THE MISSION (2022-2025)	9
FIGURE 3.	MISSION OCEAN & WATERS PROJECTS ECOSYSTEM	10
FIGURE 4.	MAP OF TOPICS OF THE WORK PROGRAMME CLUSTER 6 2023/2024, WHICH CONTRIBUTE TO MISSION GOALS & REQUIRE CITIZEN/STAKEHOLDER PARTICIPATION, REGARDING THE MISSION GOAL.	18
FIGURE 5.	REQUIREMENTS FOR STAKEHOLDER/CITIZEN PARTICIPATION IN THE TOPICS ADDRESSING THE MISSIONS GOALS IN EACH BASIN.	19
FIGURE 6.	SCREENSHOT OF THE STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT METHODS ONLINE TOOL (SOURCE: WAVELINKS).	24
FIGURE 7.	DETAIL PAGE FOR THE METHOD "WORLD CAFE" (SOURCE: WAVELINKS).....	25
FIGURE 8.	SCREENSHOT OF THE V0.3 OF THE TOOL THAT ILLUSTRATE THE SELECTION OF FILTERS BY THE USERS.	25
FIGURE 9.	SUMMARY OF STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT WEBINARS, HELD BETWEEN JULY AND OCTOBER 2024. SOURCE: AUTHORS' ELABORATION.....	27
FIGURE 10.	KEY RECOMMENDATIONS BY PREP4BLUE ON STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT IN MISSION OCEAN & WATERS.....	34

Executive Summary

Prep4Blue, as a Coordination and Support Action (CSA), contributed to setting the foundation for the successful implementation of the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030.” A central focus of the project was to support public mobilization— one of the Mission’s enablers—by developing strategies, tools, and activities to engage both citizens and stakeholders in Mission-relevant research and innovation.

To address this goal, Prep4Blue established two dedicated work packages:

- **WP3 focused on citizens**, defined as non-specialist individuals acting outside formal organizational structures.
- **WP6 addressed stakeholders**, understood as organised actors such as public authorities, businesses, researchers, NGOs, and civil society.

Prep4Blue’s activities supported both groups through:

- The development of **stakeholder engagement guidelines** and a **dedicated online tool (WaveLinks)** to help future Mission projects choose suitable engagement methods.
- The launch of a **Mission engagement Helpdesk**, along with a series of stakeholder and citizen-focused webinars to support knowledge sharing and capacity building.
- **Engaged research with citizen networks**, and training workshops focused on ocean literacy, behaviour change, and inclusive participation.
- The organisation of **pilot stakeholder assemblies** and the creation of a **Community of Practice**, which brought together actors from across Europe to test participatory and collaborative approaches in support of Mission objectives.

Despite this methodological approach, throughout its lifetime, Prep4Blue recognised the fluidity between citizens and stakeholders, while maintaining separate engagement strategies tailored to the needs of each. The tools, resources, and lessons generated by the project are now available for use by Horizon Europe projects and other Mission-aligned initiatives, helping to ensure that public engagement is inclusive, meaningful, and aligned with the 2030 goals of the Mission.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and the document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
CoP(s)	Community(ies) of Practice
CSA(s)	Coordination and Support Action project(s)
CSO(s)	Civil and civic Society Organisation(s)
HD	(Prep4Blue Stakeholder Engagement) HelpDesk
LH(s)	LightHouse(s)
Mission (Ocean & Waters)	Mission “Restore Our Oceans and Waters”
P4B	Prep4Blue
SH	Stakeholder(s)
SH(s)	StakeHolder(s)
SHEM(s)	Stakeholder Engagement Method(s)
SHES	Stakeholder Engagement Strategy
WP	Work Packages

1 Introduction

1.1 Mission “Restore Our Ocean and Waters”

The EU Missions are a new way to bring in concrete solutions to some of Europe's greatest challenges. Prep4Blue's Mission of interest is the Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters (by 2030) which will deliver impact through implementing a new role for R&I, create a portfolio of actions, implement new forms of governance and collaboration, citizen's participation.

The Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters (hereafter 'the Mission' or 'Mission Ocean & Waters') has 3 main objectives and 2 enablers (Figure 1). Each objective has 3 quantitative targets. The objectives and targets are as follows:

1. Protect and Restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, in line with the EU Biodiversity Strategy by 2030
 - a. Protect at least 30% and strictly protect 10% EU's Sea areas
 - b. Restore 25,000 km free flowing rivers
 - c. Marine nature restoration targets (incl. degraded seabeds, coastal ecosystems)
2. Prevent and Eliminate pollution of our oceans, seas and waters, in line with the EU Action Plan Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil
 - a. Reduce by at least 50% plastic litter
 - b. Reduce by at least 30% microplastics
 - c. Reduce by at least 50% nutrient losses, chemical pesticides
3. Make the sustainable Blue Economy carbon-neutral and circular, in line with the proposed European Climate Law and the holistic vision enshrined in the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy
 - a. Net zero maritime emissions,
 - b. Zero carbon aquaculture,
 - c. Low carbon multipurpose use of marine space.

To support its objectives, the Mission deploys two key enablers:

- A digital ocean and water knowledge system to enhance monitoring, forecasting, and decision-making (*e.g., Digital Twin Ocean, etc.*)
- Public mobilization through Participatory governance and/or public engagement, citizen science, and social innovation, enabling citizens to drive the transition (*e.g., co-creation and co-design; Citizen Science; Education, Literacy & Awareness; Stewardship and volunteering; etc.*).

Mission objectives and targets

Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030

Figure 1. Mission Objectives and Enablers (Source: European Commission)

A new concept implemented within the Mission, is *LightHouse (LH)*. Mission lighthouses (LHs) are sites to test, demonstrate, and deploy the Mission activities across EU seas and river basins. They try out new ideas and involve local businesses and people in the process. So far, the Mission has 4 LHs (see Figure 2):

- Baltic & North Sea basins
- Mediterranean Sea basin
- Danube river basin & Black Sea basin
- Atlantic & Arctic Sea basins

Figure 2. Mission Lighthouses and their specific objective in the first phase of the Mission (2022-2025)

The Mission is, currently, split in 2 phases:

- First phase (2022-2025): Development and piloting
- Second phase (2026-2030): Deployment and upscaling

During the first phase of the Mission, each of the Lighthouses focused on one (out of the three) objectives (Figure 2). Each LH has also a dedicated CSA (*Coordination and Support Action*) project dedicated to their basin and objective. Therefore, there are four LH CSA projects (BlueMissionAA, BlueMissionBANOS, BlueMissionMed & EcoDaLLi) with Prep4Blue acting as the overarching and coordinating CSA project (Figure 3).

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Figure 3. Mission Ocean & Waters projects Ecosystem

1.2 Stakeholder engagement in the Mission

Stakeholder engagement is a cornerstone of the Mission Ocean and Waters, driving collaborative governance, citizen participation, and digital engagement. To restore marine and freshwater ecosystems, eliminate pollution, and advance a carbon-neutral and circular blue economy, the Mission unites efforts across sectors and governance levels, ensuring that all actors contribute meaningfully. By mobilizing citizens and stakeholders, it fosters transformative change, empowering the public to protect this vital common good.

In line with Article 2(6) of the [Horizon Europe Regulation \(EU No 2021/695\)](#), the 2021-2025 piloting phase established Lighthouses as hubs for innovation, demonstration, and deployment in key sea and river basins. These Lighthouses integrate stakeholder engagement through co-design and co-implementation, ensuring participation from local communities, businesses, and researchers.

The 2026-2030 deployment and upscaling phase will refine, expand, and replicate piloted solutions across the EU and neighbouring basins. Stakeholder engagement will remain central, with citizen-driven participatory research and innovation. Scale-up actions will advance R&I outcomes to higher

TRLs, accelerate market entry, and support new solutions through EU funds and interdisciplinary collaborations.

Restoring the hydrosphere requires tackling unsustainable exploitation, pollution, climate change, and knowledge gaps through an integrated, systemic approach. The Mission fosters long-term stakeholder collaboration across European, national, and regional levels, incorporating elements of renewed ocean and water governance as outlined by the Mission Board. Given the ambition and scope of the Mission, a dedicated Mission Enabler was introduced to empower individuals and communities to actively contribute to its objectives.”

1.3 Mission enabler “Public mobilization and engagement”

In line with Article 7(3) of the [Horizon Europe Regulation](#), the Mission Ocean and Waters promotes broad public mobilization and stakeholder engagement, while also empowering citizens and local communities through participation, co-creation, and education to drive the restoration and sustainable management of aquatic ecosystems. To foster direct participation and enable individuals and communities to actively contribute to the Mission's objectives, citizen engagement is promoted in line with the Mission’s citizen engagement expected outcomes (below taken from the [Mission Ocean & Waters Implementation Plan](#)):

By 2025:

- Tried and applied deliberative democracy mechanisms and social innovation practices for the co-design and co-implementation of solutions for the restoration of the aquatic environment.
- Developed and piloted frameworks and processes for participatory governance and deliberative democracy, including an EU-wide network of assemblies to enable effective citizen and stakeholder involvement in the lighthouses.
- Up-scaled the European Research Area funded pilot citizen science campaign “Plastic Pirates – Go Europe” together with further Member States.
- Involved the European solidarity corps in restoration projects.
- Promoted apps allowing citizens to collect data and observations and promoted (digital) data collection and participatory research involving citizens for the monitoring and restoration of ocean and waters; the collected data has to be harmonised and made publicly available through the Digital Twin Ocean, EMODnet and/or the Copernicus Marine Service.
- Provided knowledge and methodological frameworks to support the revision of the International Ocean Governance agenda.

By 2030

- All European citizens have the opportunity to engage in the preservation and restoration of oceans and waters through participative means, volunteering and citizen science.
- All European citizens are empowered to be actors in the preservation and restoration of oceans and waters through social innovation, awareness raising, education and training.
- Promoted EU-wide annual ocean literacy campaigns, in cooperation with the EU4Ocean Coalition to strengthen public awareness and overcome the emotional disconnect with the ocean and waters.
- Launched regular citizen science campaigns as a part of novel participatory research initiatives to increase the reach, quality and impact of scientific initiatives and boost the environmental awareness of the participants.

To integrate stakeholders, experts, and policymakers into decision-making processes, ensuring an inclusive and representative governance model, the Mission promotes:

- Deliberative democracy platforms at EU, national, regional, and macroregional/sea basin levels, fostering engagement and co-creation, while leveraging existing initiatives where appropriate.
- Stakeholder Assemblies at regional, macroregional, or basin levels, ensuring bottom-up participation in Mission Lighthouses and scale-up actions to reflect local priorities and drive impactful solutions.

Stakeholder dialogues and co-governance initiatives, enabling policymakers, researchers, businesses, and civil society to align strategies for sustainable ocean and water management

1.4 Stakeholder engagement and public mobilization in Prep4Blue: Citizen(s) vs Stakeholders(s)

- Prep4Blue had two Work Packages (WP) dedicated to Stakeholder Engagement and the enabler “public mobilization”: WP3 – *Citizens: Empowering Citizens to Engage with the Mission and Implement activities to support the Mission*
- WP6 – *Stakeholder Engagement: Strategy, Connectivity and Capacity Building*

Their aim was, for WP3 “*To ensure active citizen participation in the co-design and co-implementation of the Mission R&I core activities*” and for WP6 “*to develop effective measures and models for impactful stakeholder engagement to co-develop and co-implement the scale-up of innovative solutions leading to the achievement of the Mission Objectives*”. As such, from an early start, Prep4Blue made a distinction between Citizens and Stakeholders.

*“The term “**citizen**” can be quite vague and is used differently across different fields (legal, political), projects, and policy areas. In general, when used in this [NDLR: Prep4Blue Citizen Engagement] toolbox, “citizen” emphasizes the non-specialist, non-elite nature of the individuals in question...**Stakeholders**, by contrast, may be either specialist, elite, have access to Mission Ocean activities due to their employment, or some other form of contextual privilege. They also tend to be represented as organisations or interest groups, while citizens tend to be engaged as individuals.”* (Source: Bjørkan et al. 2023. [Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean and Waters: A toolbox of approaches](#)).

Therefore, for analytical purposes and to target different Mission priorities, Prep4Blue chose to approach these as two different categories, in two different WPs. Indeed, the same definition has been recalled in the Executive Summary as well as in the Introduction of *Deliverable D6.1 - Stakeholder Engagement Guidelines* – to clarify that the document and its analyses were conducted following this shared definition between the two WPs in order to coordinate their purposes and targets. Nonetheless, there have been overlaps, as all stakeholder representatives are also citizens, and who is considered to “have a stake”, as a citizen or a stakeholder, depends on the questions raised and the specific context. Prep4Blue recognized this potential overlapping clearly stating in D6.1 that “*the two concepts often overlap and, of course, individual stakeholders can also be citizens, and citizens may be stakeholders*”. This distinction, indeed, could not always be replicated across the project (e.g., stakeholders sometimes appearing in WP6 as ‘anyone with a stake’) and an acknowledgement of the fluidity between the terms citizen and stakeholder remained to some extent.

First, in some cases, engagement methods that specifically target either citizens (as individuals) or stakeholders (e.g., CSOs or local communities), while not equivalent, often overlap or share

similarities. In other cases, both groups are involved in the same process (e.g., community-level participatory planning), or no distinction is made at the methodological level. Moreover, the European Commission itself consistently uses the combined “citizen/stakeholder” terminology when referring to these actors in Mission Ocean and Waters funding calls — including the call under which Prep4Blue was funded.

While the [Citizen Engagement Toolbox \(Bjørkan et al. 2023\)](#) developed by Prep4Blue provides a typology that illustrates this complexity — and offers guidance on when and how to include specific actors (stakeholders, citizens, etc.) — it must be acknowledged that, in the case of WP6, the aggregation of citizens and CSOs into a single category was often replicated. This was particularly true when collecting and analysing stakeholder engagement methods from literature and other projects or initiatives, as reflected in *D6.2 “Stakeholder engagement recommendations for future key Mission R&I core activities”* and the WaveLinks tool. This was due to the fact that the available data and sources were already aggregated and did not support the application of the more nuanced distinction made in Prep4Blue and outlined above.

2 Citizen engagement by Prep4Blue: Methods and results

Prep4Blue approached citizen engagement as a distinct yet complementary component to stakeholder engagement, recognizing citizens as non-specialist individuals acting outside of formal organizational structures. While overlaps with stakeholders were acknowledged, Prep4Blue deliberately developed dedicated activities and methodologies to empower citizens to co-design and co-implement Mission Ocean & Waters actions. Through a variety of participatory formats—including engaged research, targeted surveys, interviews, and training workshops—Prep4Blue mobilized diverse citizen networks across Europe. This section outlines the approaches and key outcomes of these efforts, showcasing how citizen involvement was fostered, evaluated, and scaled throughout the project.

2.1 Engaged research among citizens networks

Of course (and as emphasised by the European Commission), the Mission is not just a research programme – it also takes place along every coast, lake and river in Europe, amongst fishing communities and everywhere that water plays a critical role in structuring social life (arguably across the whole continent), and consequently grounding value-sensitive decisions based on uncertain scientific knowledge, with a diversity of relevant knowledge producers. The T3.4 team employed engaged research among target networks as a way of engaging with and supporting these on-the-ground communities and networks (as detailed in [Deliverable D3.3](#) on the results of those). Engaged research employs methods that “*share a common interest in collaborative engagement with the community and aim to improve, understand or investigate an issue of public interest or concern, including societal challenges. Engaged research is advanced with community partners rather than for them (Campus Engage 2022).*” Prep4Blue team members conducted engaged research among three different citizen-engaged Communities of Practice (CoP): coastal and riparian communities, ocean literacy networks, and ocean sciences & arts. These were first selected at project proposal stage due to their relevance to Mission Ocean and Waters’ objectives and on the basis that they all performed citizen engagement activities. To facilitate engaged research, the final list was decided based either on the physical proximity of the relevant organisations to Prep4Blue partners (*e.g.*, Catalan Ocean Literacy Network for the Institute of Marine Sciences (ICM), or pre-existing relationships with Prep4Blue partners (*e.g.*, the Irish Ocean Literacy Network for ERINN Innovation Ltd). The full list of networks/groups engaged is as follows: Barcelona Ocean Cities Network, the Irish Ocean Literacy Network, the Ocean Literacy Italia network, the Catalan/Spanish Ocean Literacy networks (Xarxa d’Escoles Marines at the Catalan level, and Red y Recursos de Educación Marina at the Spanish level, Reeducamar), and Blue Genes ocean science and arts network.

The overall engaged research strategy was to examine how to best facilitate and support scalable, Mission-focused initiatives as examples of how citizen-engaged networks can be facilitated to align with the Mission’s targets. The CoPs from the different locations were networked through the engaged research team, acting as a coordinating hub. In this way, the different organisations and CoPs could capacitate each other to strategically develop them all.

2.2 Pre/post engagement surveys

Prep4Blue has engaged with a variety of Mission Ocean & Waters actors – Mission-funded project teams, EC officials, marine advocacy networks, coastal communities. Efforts have been made to co-design and evaluate as much of this work as possible to ensure relevance to the community, and to track impact.

2.2.1 Pre-engagement survey

From October 2022 – January 2023, the Prep4Blue team undertook a needs analysis of those who engage citizens in marine and freshwater activities across Europe and its waters. The aims of the study were to examine the organisations and projects working on citizen engagement in the space, and to assess their needs in terms of engaging with Mission targets and activities. The study was conducted as an online survey, which was translated into 11 languages and disseminated through research, advocacy, industry, and community networks around Europe. This included online forums such as the Ocean Decade Comms Forum, Sustainable Ocean Alliance’s Europe Forum, and through The Marine Social Science Network’s monthly newsletter. The survey received 229 responses, of which 92 were deemed invalid due to being incomplete. This left 137 valid responses from 26+ different countries (some were globally active). Respondents included individuals, R&I institutions, ocean literacy and advocacy groups, NGOs, and government agencies and policymakers.

2.2.2 Post-engagement surveys

Across 2023 and 2024, Prep4Blue delivered a webinar series titled “*Planning for Citizen Participation in Mission Ocean and Waters*” (Episodes can be found here: prep4blue.eu/portfolio/prep4blue-citizen-engagement-webinar-series). Following these or other similar workshops, short online surveys were circulated to all participants. This enabled the collection of feedback regarding the relevance and quality of the training. One key open question was always asked: “what other training could we offer you to help you better engage citizens in marine and freshwater matters?” The answers were then thematically coded into five overarching themes – How to do stakeholder engagement, issue-specific needs, how to apply methods in practice, funding, and communications. From a total of 549 training participants in 2023, 106 returned post-engagement evaluations (a response rate of 19%). Aside from influencing and streamlining the design of future capacity building resources developed by Prep4Blue, these periodic surveys provided an insight into the challenges being experienced by the emerging Mission Ocean & Waters citizen engagement Community of Practice (CoP) as Phase One of the Mission - “Developing and Piloting (2022 – 2025)” advanced.

2.3 Interviews with participants/representatives of aquatic citizen science initiatives

Over spring and summer 2023, interviews were carried out with aquatic citizen science initiatives from across Europe. The aim of the interviews was to share perspectives and recommendations for others starting or running aquatic citizen science projects. These were selected from a database of 1000 aquatic citizen science initiatives built by the Prep4Blue team (eventually published open access as an interactive resource on the [“WaveLinks” platform](#)). As a preliminary step, the initiatives on the database were invited to participate in a short survey to assess the state of aquatic citizen science across Europe, of which 98 responded (roughly 10%), indicating that they were open to participating in a follow-on interview. From these, 14 interviewees were selected based on project topic, project scope, project duration and whether there is a remarkable facet to the project that might be interesting to discuss further.

In all, 14 semi-structured interviews of approximately one-hour were held via video conferences. These covered various themes (biodiversity, plastic pollution, historical climate change, coastal dynamics, entanglements in small-scale fisheries, and more). By choosing a semi-structured interview, a backbone of questions was set, but the interview structure allowed flexibility to explore emerging

topics. This also allowed flexibility for the interviewer to ask additional questions if a certain topic seems interesting or relevant to the project.

To extract usable information from these interviews, qualitative inductive coding was used, executed in the coding program “Taguette”. In this coding method, the qualitative data is the starting point of the coding process. From there, a ground-up approach is used to derive the codes from the data instead of starting with preconceived notions of what the codes should be. The codes used in the analysis are deducted along the way and allow the narrative of the coding to emerge from the raw transcribed data itself. The themes arising guided us to the parts of aquatic citizen science that needed extra information or guidance. During the interview analysis, interesting quotes supporting a reoccurring finding were kept separate to include in the report. All interviewee quotes are anonymised. The full results of Prep4Blue’s surveys and interviews of European aquatic citizen science were published in the report *Beneath the Surface* ([Debaveye et al. 2023](#)).

2.4 Citizen Engagement Training Workshops

Between 2022 and 2024, Prep4Blue developed a [suite of citizen engagement training workshops](#). These have been designed to empower those engaged in Mission Ocean & Waters-relevant activities to align their work with the citizen engagement targets of the Mission, while increasing social inclusion, reach, and overall success of aquatic research and advocacy. All information is available in deliverable [D3.2 “A synthesis report containing bespoke legacy training resources to support citizen action”](#).

The citizen engagement training delivered by PREP4BLUE was organised under four themes:

- i) Fostering sustainable behaviour change
- ii) Fostering volunteerism and promoting activism
- iii) Encouraging social cohesion and social inclusion
- iv) Evaluation and impact assessment

➔ **Citizen engagement training workshops Available through Prep4Blue’s website:** <https://prep4blue.eu/portfolio/prep4blue-citizen-engagement-webinar-series/>

3 Stakeholder engagement: preliminary analysis, methods identification and results

Stakeholder (SH) engagement was mainly handled through WP6. Prep4Blue started with a desktop study of Work programmes and Mission baseline studies (see section 3.1). This was afterwards followed by the stakeholder engagement guideline ([D6.1](#) & section 3.3.1), the development of a Community of Practices (CoP) (see section 3.4) and a toolkit of stakeholder engagement methods (section 3.3.2 & [WaveLinks Stakeholder Engagement Methods](#)). These were used then as basis for a first set of SH engagement recommendation for future Mission activities (section 4.2 & [D6.2](#)) as well as for the organisation of Pilot Stakeholder Assemblies (section 3.4 & [D6.3](#)). Deriving from these, Prep4Blue implemented a series of webinars on stakeholder engagement in the Mission (section 3.3.3) and a Helpdesk for supporting their uptake (section 3.3.4 & [D6.4](#)). Another desktop study as well as interviews were used to inform the capacity building needs for SH engagement (section 3.6 & [D6.5](#)) and to identify the necessary skills for addressing them as well as to achieve the Mission targets (Section 3.3.3, section 3.6 & [D6.5](#)).

3.1 Desktop study for Stakeholder engagement in and for the Mission

The desktop study’s focus was to analyse the stakeholder engagement requirements listed in the Work programs (2021-2022 & 2023-2024) of the *Missions* and *Cluster 6 “Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment”*. This was then later on completed by the analysis of the Mission baseline studies¹.

For a more efficient and impactful research, the work programmes analysis was conducted in several steps:

1. Selection of keywords by category/types of keywords (Table 2). Each category was assigned a specific colour.

Table 2. Analysis criteria for stakeholder engagement in the Missions and Cluster 6 work programs of 2021-2022 and 2023-2024.

Category/Types of keywords		Keywords used
Highlights concerning the Mission Ocean and Waters and/or its objectives	Ocean/Water related	“Restore Our Ocean and Waters”, “Ocean”, “Water”, “Marine”, “Coastal”, “Coast”, “Aquatic”, “Aquaculture”, “River”, “Freshwater”
	Mission Ocean Objectives	“Pollution”, “Biodiversity”, “Circular economy”, “carbon”, “circular life(cycle)”, “Plastic”, “Restore”
Highlights concerning stakeholder (SH) engagement/involvement	Stakeholder categories and Stakeholder engagement	“Stakeholder(s)”, “Policy maker(s)”, “Management”, “Authorities”, “SSH (Social Science and Humanities)”, “bring together”, etc.
Highlights concerning policy, legislation and regulations	Policy	“Policy”, “MSFD”, “WFD”, “Directive”, “European Green Deal”, “River Basin Management Plan”, “good ecological status”, “SRIA”, “Biodiversity strategy”, “Galway Statement”, “Belém Statement”, etc.
Highlights concerning links needed with other Work Programmes, Calls, Topics, Projects, etc.	Other EU initiatives	“Open science practices”, “European Marine Observation and Data network (EMODnet)”, “Copernicus”, “previous EU framework programmes”, “Horizon 2020”, “national and regional programmes”, “Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership”, “Biodiversa+”, “LIFE”, “EMFF/EMFAF”, “HORIZON-INFRA”, “OSPAR”

2. Visual analysis of the topics (looking for highlight colours). When a topic had several hits (several highlighted colours) from several keyword categories (see step 1), then the topic was preselected.
3. The preselected topics were then read more in depth to see if they were relevant. A topic was considered relevant if it had links/mentions of the Mission Ocean and Waters or one of its objectives and asked for Stakeholder engagement. It ended up with 93 relevant topics: 56 for the *Cluster 6* work programs and 37 for the *Missions* work programs (Table 3 & Figure 4).

¹ Baseline study for the implementation of lighthouses of the Mission ‘Restore our ocean and waters by 2030’: Atlantic, Arctic, Danube and Mediterranean lighthouses (doi: [10.2777/34856](https://doi.org/10.2777/34856)) & Baltic and North Sea Lighthouse (doi: [10.2777/96040](https://doi.org/10.2777/96040))

Table 3. Number of topics per Work Program (Missions & Cluster 6) and per Year (2021-2022 & 2023-2024) asking for Stakeholder Engagement

Work Programme Destination/Call	Year		Total
	2021-2022	2023-2024	
Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment (Cluster 6)		56	56
Biodiversity and ecosystem services		10	10
Circular economy and bioeconomy sectors		18	18
Clean environment and zero pollution		7	7
Fair, healthy and environment-friendly food systems from primary production to consumption		8	8
Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the Green Deal		3	3
Land, ocean and water for climate action		5	5
Other actions not subject to calls for proposals		1	1
Resilient, inclusive, healthy and green rural, coastal and urban communities		4	4
Missions (HORIZON-MISS)	24	13	37
Actions for the implementation of the Mission Restore our ocean and waters by 2030	10		10
Joint Demonstration	1	2	3
Mission Enabling activities: Digital knowledge system, public mobilisation and engagement, dynamic investment ecosystem	3	4	7
Preparation for deployment of 'lighthouse demonstrators' and solution scale ups and cross-cutting citizen and stakeholder involvement	1		1
Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters	2		2
Sustainable, carbon-neutral and circular Blue economy	2	4	6
Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity	5	3	8
Total	24	69	93

Figure 4. Map of topics of the Work programme Cluster 6 2023/2024, which contribute to Mission goals & require citizen/stakeholder participation, regarding the Mission goal.

The topics selected as relevant were then further analysed to extract 2 key information:

- the stakeholders to be involved,
- the actions/methods required to involve the stakeholders.

3.1.1 Stakeholders to be involved in the Mission based on desktop study

In the Mission Work programs (2021-2022 & 2023-2024), some of the requirements for stakeholder and/or citizen participation in the research projects are shared by most of the topics, as depicted in Figure 5 by the grey box. The other boxes contain information about the stakeholders' categories that should be involved in the research projects. Most of these categories were not explicitly stated in the topic's description: this is an initial map of Stakeholders that Prep4Blue has established from this analysis, which had to be fine-tuned in collaboration with the LH CSAs.

EUROPEAN BLUE PARKS	DANUBE	ATLANTIC / ARCTIC	MED	BALTIC / NORTH SEA
<p>LONG TERM MANAGEMENT OF SOLUTIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Citizen participation, European Volunteer Corps and Mission Citizen Assemblies, Ocean literacy networks, consumer involvement ✓ NGOs for conservation, raising awareness, education ✓ Regional and local authorities, policy makers. Sometimes national and transnational levels are required ✓ Local business communities, in particular SMEs, investors and other business stakeholders → Business models for generating revenue from the solutions ✓ Engage 3-5 'associated regions' to showcase the feasibility, replicability and scale up of the solutions, enable them to follow closely the project and provide them with technical assistance to build capacity <p>SYNERGIES: Engage with other projects</p>				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Land & Sea use planning decision-makers ▪ MPAs managers ▪ Conservationists ▪ Natura 2000, National Parks, Biosphere Reserves ▪ Business stakeholders (fishing, aquaculture, tourist sectors, wind farms, transports, oil companies...) ▪ Networks of Parks, ex. MedPAN ▪ Seaweed restoration initiatives and algae farming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Waste water treatment plants ▪ Water agencies ▪ NGOs ▪ Conservationists ▪ Managers of protected areas ▪ National/local authorities for natural risk prevention ▪ Farming ▪ Territorial concertation experts ▪ ICPDR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Water treatment ▪ Ports, cities, urban planners ▪ Risk prevention authorities ▪ Business stakeholders (Fishing, aquaculture, tourist sectors, wind farms, transports, oil companies...) ▪ EU Outermost Regions ▪ ICPDR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ports, cities, urban planners ▪ Land owners, soil managers ▪ Water managers, river management authorities ▪ Water treatment ▪ Recycling ▪ Risk prevention authorities ▪ Business stakeholders (fishing, aquaculture, tourist sectors, transports, oil companies, recycling...) ▪ Diplomacy North/South 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fishing, aquaculture, tourist sectors, wind farms, energy industry, transports, oil companies ▪ Consumers ▪ Policy makes

Figure 5. Requirements for stakeholder/citizen participation in the topics addressing the Missions goals in each basin.

Based on the analysis and using the Penta-Helix Model for stakeholder engagement, a first list of stakeholders to be involved to achieve Mission targets was crafted:

- **Government / Public authorities** which include the Local, Regional, National and International Authorities: Local and regional public authorities (municipalities, coastal zone managers); National government representatives and ministries (e.g., environment, fisheries, marine); European Commission and EU Agencies; International policy bodies (e.g., UN Decade of Ocean Science, GEO Blue Planet); Policy makers and regulators; Representatives from governance at various scales (local to international); Decision makers in marine and water policy; Environmental protection agencies; Policy communities.
- **Academia / Research and Education**, also sometimes coined as Scientific and Research Institutions: Universities and marine research institutes; SSH (Social Sciences and Humanities) researchers; Natural and environmental scientists; Oceanographic institutions; All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance; Research infrastructures (e.g., EU PolarNET2, SCAR, etc.); Multidisciplinary research communities.
- **Industry / Business sector** also known as the Private Sector: Businesses including SMEs; Blue economy sectors (fisheries, aquaculture, marine renewable energy, coastal tourism); Agricultural and forestry actors; Marine technology providers; Industry actors along the food and marine value chains; Advisors and consultants.

- **Civil Society / Communities**, also known as Community-Based and Societal Stakeholders: Civil society organizations (including NGOs); Local and indigenous communities (Arctic, coastal, island); Citizen science networks; Rural and urban communities; Youth, women, and vulnerable groups; Farmers and fishers; Consumers; Citizen groups and environmental stewards; Cultural heritage custodians.
- **Media / Knowledge Brokers / Communication Actors** also seen as Information Disseminators and Connectors (Ocean literacy): Science communicators; Journalists and environmental media; Citizen science platforms; Public engagement facilitators; Knowledge exchange networks; Observation communities (marine and coastal); Platforms for co-design, communication, and dissemination.
- **Cross-Cutting / Hybrid stakeholders**: All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance; UN Decade of Ocean Science; Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership; International Ocean governance bodies (*e.g.*, OSPAR, HELCOM); Indigenous knowledge holders working with scientists; Climate science and operational oceanography communities.

3.1.2 *Actions/Methods to involve the Stakeholders based on desktop study*

The success of Mission Ocean and Waters relies on the active involvement of diverse stakeholders representing a broad spectrum of expertise and interests (see section 3.1.1). Based on the desktop analysis, to achieve the Mission's targets, stakeholders should participate in various types of actions, ensuring a holistic and comprehensive approach:

1. **Collaborative Research and Innovation:** Researchers, technology providers, and industry representatives should collaborate to develop innovative solutions for sustainable water treatment, conservation practices, and the circular economy in the marine and water sector. Involvement in co-design and co-creation processes is crucial to ensure solutions that are effective, socially acceptable, and economically viable.
2. **Policy and Decision-Making:** Policymakers, regulators, and government representatives play a vital role in creating an enabling environment for sustainable practices. Their engagement is essential for setting regulations, incentives, and standards that promote water and marine conservation, circular economy initiatives, and responsible water use.
3. **Community Engagement and Empowerment:** Local authorities, communities, and indigenous groups should actively participate in decision-making processes to ensure that initiatives are aligned with local needs, culture, and traditions. Their engagement can help implement context-specific strategies that support social inclusion, well-being, and resilience.
4. **Knowledge Exchange and Education:** Researchers, experts, and knowledge institutions should collaborate to develop training programs, workshops, and capacity-building initiatives. This empowers young professionals and stakeholders with the necessary skills to contribute effectively to sustainable water and marine management practices.
5. **Business and Industry Engagement:** Businesses, including SMEs, play a crucial role in adopting sustainable practices. They can participate in circular economy initiatives, explore eco-innovative solutions, and create value by aligning their operations with the principles of responsible water use.

6. **Citizen Science and Engagement:** Engaging citizens and consumers is vital to raise awareness about the importance of water conservation and circular (blue) economy practices. Their involvement in citizen science projects and decision-making processes can enhance social acceptance and contribute to behavioural change.
7. **Cross-Sectoral Collaboration:** Collaboration across sectors, such as agriculture, tourism, fisheries, and energy, is essential for integrated water and marine management. Bringing together stakeholders from different sectors can lead to innovative solutions that address shared challenges and maximize synergies.
8. **International Cooperation:** Collaboration with international initiatives, organizations, and research networks enhances the exchange of knowledge, best practices, and solutions. This fosters a global approach to sustainable management, aligning efforts to address transboundary challenges.

By fostering inclusive governance, knowledge sharing, and participatory approaches, Mission Ocean and Waters can harness the collective expertise of these stakeholders to develop holistic solutions that promote environmental sustainability, economic growth, social well-being, and resilience in the face of water/marine-related challenges.

Here below (Table 4), you can find a first try, based on the 2021-2022 and 2023-2024 Work programs, in crossing the stakeholders with the actions they are required to participate and or co-design/co-create in/for Mission Ocean and Waters.

Table 4. Stakeholder engagement action type with the required stakeholders

Action Type	Stakeholders Involved
Policy development and governance	Governments, NGOs, academia, indigenous groups
Research and innovation	Universities, research institutions, businesses, civil society
Capacity building	Education bodies, SMEs, youth, NGOs
Data collection and monitoring	Scientists, citizens, indigenous communities
Knowledge exchange	Media, knowledge brokers, industry, research networks
Climate adaptation and resilience	Local communities, public authorities, planners
Sustainable food and marine economy	Farmers, fishers, aquaculture sector, SMEs, consumers
Cultural and traditional knowledge integration	Indigenous peoples, heritage organizations
Awareness and behavioural change	Citizens, NGOs, communicators, educators

3.2 Stakeholders addressed by Prep4Blue

The comprehensive desktop study of the Horizon Europe Work Programme and associated Mission documents (section 3.1) served to preliminarily identify the broad spectrum of stakeholders to be addressed under the Mission, as well as the actions and methods needed to engage them. This stakeholder analysis was further developed during the preparation of *Deliverable D6.1 – Stakeholder Engagement Guidelines* (section 3.3.1) – and through the development of the *WaveLinks web platform* (section 3.3.2).

However, Prep4Blue's core function as a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) meant that it did not aim to directly mobilize every stakeholder category. Rather, Prep4Blue served as a foundational platform and enabler, preparing the ground for future Mission-funded R&I projects and initiatives to engage stakeholders across the penta-helix model. As such, the primary stakeholders Prep4Blue addressed were not sectoral groups per se, but rather the R&I actors and consortia who will themselves seek to engage sector-specific stakeholders in line with the Mission's evolving needs.

This approach was reflected in several key activities:

- Strategic support: *Deliverable D6.1* (section 3.3.1) provided a structured framework and toolkit for stakeholder identification, categorization, and engagement using the penta-helix model.
- Operational tools: The WaveLinks platform (section 3.3.2) aggregated and systematized engagement approaches and stakeholder mappings to support future projects in matching needs with engagement strategies.
- Capacity-building (section 3.6): Prep4Blue delivered training resources, helpdesk support, and methodological guidance to build capacity among upcoming Mission implementers to run inclusive and effective stakeholder engagement processes.
- Pilot actions (section 3.5): Task 6.3 supported experimental stakeholder assemblies in collaboration with other CSAs, testing participatory and deliberative methods that could be scaled or replicated across the Mission landscape.

In sum, Prep4Blue's stakeholder engagement work did not directly target the entire stakeholder landscape initially identified, but instead focused on empowering future Mission actors to do so. These include projects funded under Horizon Europe, national or regional initiatives aligned with the Mission's objectives, and thematic networks seeking to implement or support the Mission.

This intermediary role was essential: by equipping these actors with evidence-based tools, tested methods, and strategic frameworks, Prep4Blue aimed to ensure that future R&I actions are better positioned to conduct inclusive, impactful, and Mission-aligned stakeholder engagement.

To this end, the data and analyses developed through the desktop study described above fed into the activities outlined in the following paragraphs. These activities further developed the findings into tools and guidelines to support Mission-funded R&I projects, as well as into pilot actions implemented in collaboration with the other CSAs.

3.3 Stakeholder engagement tools

Building on the desktop study and the Stakeholder Engagement Recommendations introduced in [D6.2](#), Prep4Blue has developed a suite of practical tools and resources to operationalise stakeholder engagement in alignment with the Mission Ocean & Waters objectives. These tools are designed to support inclusive, informed, and impactful stakeholder participation across sectors and regions. From detailed guidelines (section 3.3.1) and a searchable method databases (WaveLinks, section 3.3.2) to training webinars (section 3.3.3) and a dedicated helpdesk (section 3.3.4), each tool helps (future) Mission stakeholders navigate the complexities of stakeholder engagement while promoting co-creation, legitimacy, and long-term impact. The following subsections present the main tools and their application within the Mission context.

3.3.1 Stakeholder engagement guidelines

Prep4Blue's deliverable [D6.1 "Stakeholder engagement guidelines including toolkit"](#) analysed how to best identify, map and approach stakeholders oriented towards the objectives set in the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters". This approach is designed to help better reaching a sustainable blue economy and the targets and objectives set in line with the Mission. The guidelines are generally applicable towards all four lighthouses: the Atlantic and Arctic Ocean, the Mediterranean Sea, the Baltic and North Sea and the Danube River and Black Sea. To support all Lighthouses and contribute to the achievement of the Mission's objectives, Prep4Blue aligned the Mission's priorities with today's most relevant stakeholder groups. Its stakeholder engagement approach was based on the Penta-Helix model, with extensions applied where necessary. As part of this effort, Prep4Blue developed a non-exhaustive stakeholder mapping, providing specific examples for each country.

From that basis, Prep4Blue's team of experts derived a "stakeholder interests and needs analysis", with cases and relevant actions that are topic and stakeholder dependent and that show how one can identify gaps and what is important working on for the application process of new projects but also towards actions in the field. This process took into account the results of the baseline studies² conducted for the lighthouses.

To support R&I projects in applying the most effective stakeholder engagement methods and in identifying the most suitable case studies for their implementation, Prep4Blue developed a database, hosted on [WaveLinks](#), showcasing several relevant projects that have been or are active within the Mission and where stakeholder engagement activities have been identified and assessed. The criteria used to select the projects and methodologies serve for future project managers and society to best select methods for stakeholder engagement, and thus successes of the project, as well as an interest for stakeholders that are directly involved as partners in projects supported or even funded by the Mission or actions that were submitted to the Mission charter and stakeholders that are engaged or to be engaged by such projects or actions. Finally, today's request to involve all kinds of stakeholders in different kinds of projects to impact the successes, reveals a gap in an overarching or governmental approach to involve stakeholders, which includes an assessment of the rights and duties of a stakeholder. It seems that currently there is a lack in precise criteria to determine the legitimacy of an interest's inclusion within the stakeholder group. These guidelines addressed this aspect as well, formulating potential approaches and frameworks to bridge the identified gap.

➔ **Stakeholder Engagement Guidelines (D6.1) Available on Prep4Blue's Zenodo community:**
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10944584>

3.3.2 WaveLinks – SH engagement method factsheet

Prep4Blue has developed an online tool ([WaveLinks > Engagement methods](#)) that can help choose the right model of engagement for projects that contribute to the Mission Ocean and Waters objectives. Below a quick overview of how the online tool looks like and what are the main functionalities of the tool. The online tool is part of the WaveLinks web platform (wavelinks.eu) jointly developed under the CSA projects Prep4Blue, BlueMissionBANOS and BlueMissionAA.

² LH baseline studies : [Baseline study for the implementation of lighthouses of the Mission 'Restore our ocean and waters by 2030' Atlantic, Arctic, Danube and Mediterranean lighthouses, Baltic and North Sea lighthouses \(European Commission - DG RTD, 2023\)](#)

The tool landing page (see Figure 6) is where the users can browse or search through the list of methods for stakeholder engagement. The initial list of methods was compiled by first identifying European projects linked to the Mission Ocean and Waters that mention stakeholder engagement in their project description or include dedicated project deliverables or results on the topic, and then by extracting and analysing the stakeholder engagement methods they applied.

Name	Targeted Groups	Level Of Engagement	Purpose Of Engagement	Participants	Duration	Data Source
> Newsletter	Media	Inform	Provide the public with ba...	Any	Ongoing	shem
> Project website	Industry Government	Inform	Present detailed descriptio...	Any	Ongoing	shem
> Social media	Government Academia Media...	Inform	Distribute small updates a...	Any	Ongoing	shem
> Printed media appearances	Media	Inform	Distribute flyers, banners, ...	Any	1-7 days	shem
> Conferences and events	Industry Government Academia...	Inform	Participate in or organize c...	50-1000	1-5 days	shem
> Joint focus workshops	Industry Government Academia...	Involve	Engage different stakehol...	10-50	1-3 days	shem
> Focus groups	Academia Government	Involve	Facilitate open discussions...	5-20	1-2 days	shem
> Summer school / winter s...	Academia Government	Involve	Provide early career resear...	20-100	3-5 days	shem
> Storymap (Infographic ve...	Media	Inform	An interactive webpage or...	Any	Ongoing	shem
> Media appearances (audio...	Media	Inform	Engage with radio, televisi...	Any	1-3 days	shem

Figure 6. Screenshot of the Stakeholder Engagement Methods Online tool (Source: WaveLinks).

Each method was then described, analysed and categorised by a group of experts in order to support navigation. Indeed, to search through the list of methods, users can use three different approaches:

- Filtering the list according to different variables: level of engagement, number of stakeholders to be engaged, targeted stakeholder groups, duration of the engagement, etc.;
- Writing in the search bar the name of a stakeholder engagement method;
- Writing in the search bar a keyword or short text that describe the topic of the project in which they want to engage stakeholders.

Two groups of users have been envisioned for the tool:

- The first group of users will already know a method they want to use to engage stakeholders in their project, and would like to get more information on how it was used in previous EU projects;
- The second group of users is looking for a relevant method of engagement to use in the context of their project. They might know which groups of stakeholders they want to engage and at which level of engagement for example, but they do not know which method they can use.

The first group of users, interested in getting more information on how a method of engagement has been used in the past in EU projects linked to the Mission is able to use the search bar and enter the name of the method to search through the list. Once the user found the method of interest in the list, they can open the detail page of the method by clicking on its name and they can see a more detailed description of the method as shown in the screenshot below (Figure 7). On the detail page, the user can also see in which context and projects the method of interest has been used in the past. The tool

displays the acronym of projects that have previously used the method (as described in their deliverables). A screenshot of the detail page of the “World Cafe” method is shown below as an example (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Detail page for the method "World Cafe" (Source: WaveLinks)

Users looking for relevant method(s) to use in the context of their Mission Ocean & Waters project can use the search bar and/or filters to look through the list of methods. They can use the filters on top of the list of methods if they already know for example the level of engagement of the stakeholders they would like to achieve. Multiple categories can be selected for each filter and once selected, the number of results will be limited to the methods that correspond to the categories selected. On the screenshot below (Figure 8), the level of engagement “inform” was selected. The list of methods is then restricted to methods that can be used to inform stakeholders.

Figure 8. Screenshot of the v0.3 of the tool that illustrate the selection of filters by the users.

Users searching for a method of engagement without much pre-conceived ideas in mind, can enter in the search bar:

- Keywords describing their project or purpose/topic of engagement;
- Free text describing the topic of their project.

When using this type of search, the algorithm of the tool looks for projects matching these keywords or free text in the list of EU projects, linked to the Mission, and that have used engagement methods (as described in their deliverables), and subsequently return to the user the methods that have been used in these similar EU projects. The method at the top of the list is the one most used in the similar projects. The list of methods used in similar projects can be refined by using the filters as described above.

The entire list of methods and/or the methods returned as the result of a user search can be exported at any time by the user as CSV file using the “CSV” button at the bottom of the list of methods.

The tool is a living tool that evolves and will get enriched along the Mission’s progress and development. For that purpose, users are able to input new stakeholder engagement methods in the database. Users can link these new methods to projects they already know have used them. These new methods will also be automatically matched to the deliverables of all projects of the database to establish more links and enrich users’ data. Input of users will be reviewed by experts before being published online.

➔ **Stakeholder Engagement Methods Factsheet Available on WaveLinks:**
<https://wavelinks.eu/explore/engagement-methods>

3.3.3 Webinars

Between 2022 and 2025, Prep4Blue developed a [suite of citizen engagement training workshops](#) (see section 2.4) and capacity building resources. It was a goal of Prep4Blue to build capacity and support stakeholder engagement with the R&I goals of the Mission Ocean and Waters. With this purpose a series of [stakeholder engagement capacity building webinars](#) were developed.

This series of six webinars (Figure 9) explored diverse approaches to stakeholder engagement and co-creation in ocean and water-related initiatives. Topics ranged from climate adaptation in aquaculture and marine biodiversity valuation, to blue economy development, water scarcity governance, and citizen engagement in river and marine conservation. Each session featured practical case studies covering all the four Lighthouse areas, providing practical insights and actionable strategies to help future projects foster collaboration and innovation. The connections across the Missions “*Ocean & Waters*” and “*Climate Change Adaptation*” were explored analysing similitudes in the stakeholder engagement landscape.

Figure 9. Summary of Stakeholder engagement webinars, held between July and October 2024.
Source: Authors' elaboration

A last webinar, entitled [“Innovative Shared Governance Practices in Maritime Regions: Opportunities and Challenges”](#), was held on 6 May 2025, aimed at showcasing best practices of shared governance models for engaging stakeholders and citizens in marine and coastal issues.

These webinars were specifically designed to address some of the critical needs identified by the project, such as advancing stakeholder engagement maturity levels and fostering co-creation among diverse actors. Stakeholder discussions and recommendations address a central question: *How can Stakeholder engagement improve the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters implementation?*

➔ **Stakeholder engagement Webinar series Available through Prep4Blue’s website:** <https://prep4blue.eu/events/prep4blue-stakeholder-engagement-webinar-series/>

3.3.4 Helpdesk

The Prep4Blue Stakeholder Engagement Helpdesk (HD) was developed as an online and expert-driven support structure offering guidance, tools, and personalised advice to Mission-funded projects. Its main purpose was to foster inclusive and effective stakeholder engagement by helping users identify and apply suitable resources and methodologies. In parallel, it promoted collaboration among the helpdesk teams of the four Mission Lighthouses CSAs, the Mission Implementation Platform (MIP), and the Prep4Blue consortium.

The helpdesk structure included a user-friendly online interface with curated resources on stakeholder engagement, citizen participation, Ocean Literacy, and knowledge transfer. Key materials included:

- A Toolbox for Citizen Engagement
- The Mission Ocean & Waters Social Media Toolkit and Digital Academy
- The Wavelinks database of engagement-related initiatives
- A shared Glossary to harmonise terminology
- Recordings from both Citizen and Stakeholder Engagement Webinar Series
- A Question and Answers section
- A list of supporting experts
- A form to facilitate interactions

➔ **P4B Helpdesk Available through Prep4Blue’s website:** <https://prep4blue.eu/helpdesk>

3.4 Stakeholder Engagement Community of Practices

Work Package 6 (WP6) aimed to develop a multidisciplinary, multistakeholder approach based on the 'Penta-Helix Model' which includes industry/businesses, public authorities, citizens/local residents, academia/the knowledge sector and associations or environmental interest groups. This model builds on a culture of collaboration and acknowledges the environment as fundamental to social innovation. One of WP6's key objectives (Objective 3) was to *"Stimulate a Community of Practice capable of facilitating collaborative processes among stakeholders."*

A Community of Practice is defined as

"A group of people who share a common interest, profession, or passion and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly"

(Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated Learning: Legitimate Peripheral Participation*. Cambridge University Press.).

Key characteristics of a Community of Practice (CoP) include:

1. Domain – A shared domain of interest that gives the community its identity. Membership implies a shared competence and commitment to this domain.
2. Community – Members engage in joint activities, discussions, and knowledge-sharing, building relationships that foster learning.
3. Practice – Members develop a shared repertoire of experiences, tools, stories, and problem-solving approaches that evolve through continued interaction.

In line with WP6's Objective 3, Prep4Blue established and nurtured a Community of Practice to support collaborative processes among stakeholders involved in the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030." This evolving, structured community was central in promoting multi-stakeholder governance and aligning local actions with broader Mission objectives.

The Stakeholder engagement CoP was launched through:

- A Co-Design Workshop (*Brussels, October 2023*), which brought together 34 external experts from 24 organisations across 12 countries. Their input helped revise Deliverables D6.1 and D6.2, shaping stakeholder engagement strategies and forming the initial CoP core.
- The release of the WaveLinks platform (*October/November 2023*), which, as an interactive tool for stakeholder mapping and Stakeholder Engagement Method (STEM) selection, played a central role in expanding the CoP through user contributions and engagement.

The CoP grew in both size and depth through:

- Co-design efforts with the four Mission Lighthouse (LH) CSAs, including tailored questionnaires and continuous dialogue in support of the co-organisation of pilot Stakeholder Assemblies.
- Integration into Regional Events (*e.g., Mission Arenas*), which provided real-world testing of stakeholder engagement approaches and facilitated regional collaboration
- The organisation of a focus group session at the Ocean Best Practices System Workshop VII (*October 2023*). This session, themed *"Storytelling and the Restoration of Ecosystems,"* attracted 104 participants from 89 entities and strengthened the CoP's thematic focus on effective communication and engagement.

The CoP was further consolidated through targeted activities:

- **Capacity needs assessment (section 3.6):**
56 open interviews were conducted; 32 experts from 25 organisations joined the CoP. By May 2025, the CoP had grown to 166 members, including 136 actively engaged participants.
- **Six thematic webinars on stakeholder engagement (section 3.3.3):**
These attracted 114 live attendees, with recordings viewed over 262 times, extending reach and impact.
- **Stakeholder Engagement Helpdesk (section 3.3.4):**
An online support service visited 700 times, reinforcing the CoP's role as a resource hub for practitioners.
- **Pilot Stakeholder Assemblies (section 3.5):**
Four large-scale events were organised across the LHs, involving 400 stakeholders. These events allowed the CoP to test, adapt, and refine its engagement methodologies.

By May 2025, the Prep4Blue's Community of Practice had grown to 166 members, including 136 actively engaged participants, thus evolving from a conceptual ambition into a robust, action-oriented platform. With cross-sectoral representation and practical tools, the CoP became an enabler of collaborative governance and stakeholder alignment in support of the Mission.

3.5 Pilot Stakeholder Assemblies

In order to test stakeholder mapping approaches aligned with the penta-helix model, support other CSAs in piloting deliberative democracy and co-design methods for stakeholder engagement, deliver concrete results, and facilitate transnational and interregional collaboration, Prep4Blue collaborated in the implementation of up to four Pilot Stakeholder Assemblies, one in each sea basin.. These events took place in the following order:

1. **BlueMissionBANOS 1st Mission Arena (Gothenburg, Sweden, Nov 14-16, 2023):** Organised by S. Pro in the framework of BlueMissionBANOS project and their involvement in Prep4Blue, this event focused on Mission objective 3 (carbon-neutral and circular blue economy) and gathered around 200 participants. The Mission Arena included a large-scale World Café with 50+ workshops to co-create a roadmap for the Western Baltic sub-region (Germany, Denmark, Sweden, and Norway). The closing session included a voting session with all participants, which finalise the test of a co-decision-making process.
2. **Mediterranean Lighthouse (Rome, Italy, May 21, 2024):** Organised by CNR, in collaboration with Prep4Blue and BlueMissionMed, it gathered around 140 participants. Entitled "*Sustainable Rivers: Bridging Local and European Initiatives*" this stakeholder assembly focused on river system management, with debates among policymakers, researchers, businesses, and NGOs. It highlighted local and regional initiatives and relevant practices to amplify their impact, from the local level to the Mediterranean and beyond.
3. **Black Sea Lighthouse (Batumi, Georgia, Nov 5-7, 2024):** Organised by CPMR, in collaboration with CNR and the project EcoDaLLi, this event connected Black Sea stakeholders with the Danube and Black Sea lighthouse. A low-scale World Café with 40 participants helped identify priorities for marine ecosystem and biodiversity restoration in the region. This event was kindly hosted by the Batumi Maritime State Academy, with the presence of representatives from Ajara Autonomous Republic.

4. **Atlantic Lighthouse (Bordeaux, France, Nov 20, 2024):** Kindly hosted by the region of Nouvelle-Aquitaine and organised by CPMR in collaboration with CETMAR and the BlueMissionAA project, this event focused on marine ecosystem restoration and biodiversity. It tested an experimental role-playing game based on Atlantic lighthouse case studies with a small group of 16 participants. It served to showcase relevant stakeholder consultation processes and assess this innovative stakeholder engagement method.

These assemblies provided valuable insights into stakeholder engagement methods, with key takeaways for future Mission's projects:

- Clear objectives and expected outcomes are essential. Aligning engagement methods with the event's goals enhances both relevance and impact. Moreover, clear goals help guide the identification of strategic stakeholder groups to be addressed. Tools such as *WaveLinks* can support the selection of appropriate approaches and assist in mapping the relevant stakeholders.
- Robust planning and organization are critical. Drafting a detailed concept note in advance facilitates task allocation, logistical coordination, and shared understanding among organizers.
- Qualified facilitators and moderators play a pivotal role. They ensure productive dialogue, keep discussions on track, and help manage group dynamics. When addressing sensitive or potentially contentious topics, involving neutral external professionals may be beneficial.
- The World Café method proved highly effective for fostering co-creation among diverse stakeholders. It can be successfully applied in both large and small-scale events, offering flexibility and inclusivity. To this end, it has demonstrated value as an effective method to be embedded within broader co-decision-making processes, serving as a preparatory step to build shared understanding, surface priorities, and establish trust among participants before formal decisions are made.
- Interactive tools such as serious games or scenario simulations, while not universally applicable, can play a key role in managing conflicts or navigating trade-offs among stakeholders. By providing a neutral and engaging setting, they lower barriers to participation, promote equal contribution, and help shift discussions away from entrenched positions. These tools are particularly effective in fostering creative thinking and mutual understanding, making them valuable assets in stakeholder engagement processes where diverse or conflicting interests need to be addressed constructively.

➔ **More information to be found in Prep4Blue Deliverable D6.3 “Report on the findings of the stakeholder assembly’s engagement pilots”:** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15112656>

3.6 Capacity building needed for Stakeholder engagement: Identifying necessary skills

The main objective of both T6.4 and T6.5 was to explore what kind of skills are needed to boost citizen and stakeholder engagement in Mission Ocean and Waters, supporting major changes for protecting and restoring the ocean and rivers and making the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular. They brought together knowledge and ideas from all Prep4Blue Work Packages, focusing on the needs of researchers, policy-makers, industry actors, and citizens. By identifying shared challenges and opportunities, [deliverable D6.5](#) provides a set of recommendations to help different groups work better together and develop the knowledge, tools, and strategies needed to achieve the Mission’s goals.

The identification of key skill needs was done through interviews, webinars, focus groups, and stakeholder consultations. **Transversal skills** (e.g., communication, stakeholder engagement, co-design) were consistently ranked as most essential, followed by technical and digital skills. Actions to **scale and replicate solutions**, and those fostering **citizen engagement**, were seen as most critical for the Mission's success.

Based on the identified needs and further analysis of the main outcomes from the various Prep4Blue working groups, a set of 19 key recommendations are structured into five groups:

1. **Communication & Awareness:** Improve information flow by centralising content across projects, develop multimedia communication materials, and clarify roles and responsibilities related to social media outreach.
2. **Social Inclusion:** Promote participation of underrepresented groups (e.g., ethnic minorities, persons with disabilities, etc.), by adopting targeted strategies and applying inclusion KPIs to monitor progress.
3. **Knowledge Transfer:** Address regional disparities by providing tailored training in under-resourced areas, establish monitoring mechanisms, and promote science diplomacy as a means to support transnational collaboration.
4. **Citizen & Stakeholder Engagement:** Involve stakeholders from the earliest stages, design appropriate incentives, cultivate long-term feedback mechanisms, and encourage the development of grassroots initiatives..
5. **Ocean Literacy:** Expand training and engagement opportunities through initiatives like EU4Ocean and other accessible online resources, aiming to raise awareness and build a shared sense of responsibility.

[Deliverable D6.5](#) emphasizes how achieving the Mission's goals depends on **inclusive, well-coordinated, and capacity-driven engagement** at all levels of society, from policymakers and researchers to citizens and local communities.

➔ **More information to be found in Prep4Blue Deliverable D6.5 "Pathways to develop capacity/skills needs to achieve the Mission targets by 2030":**
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15543860>

4 Recommendations from Prep4Blue

4.1 Citizen Engagement recommendations

4.1.1 Context/Issue

A need remains to much more broadly and deeply communicate Mission Ocean and Waters and its value beyond the core stakeholder groups and across European society at large. The European Commission's aim of having coastal communities and on-the-ground stakeholders across the continent take ownership of the Mission in a meaningful way has yet to be achieved.

A key issue here is a perceived lack of tangible benefit or added value to communities (*i.e.*, fishers, coastal community members, youth organisations, community led local development organisations, marine advocacy groups, citizen science groups, etc.) offered by the Mission. It is frequently noted that grassroots organisations, despite having worked effectively for years with minimal funding, often receive limited support, while large-scale projects or programmes may secure substantial budgets despite delivering only superficial impacts.

Stakeholder fatigue about being asked to participate without compensation in more and more initiatives and a more general societal perception of increased regulation/requirement relating to sustainability without reward.

4.1.2 Recommendation

Stipulate much more use of Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) in Mission Ocean and Waters Call Topics to provide consistent and tangible benefit to the communities and small organisations that engage with research projects but are not yet sufficiently capable of becoming involved in project consortia.

It was very positive to see the community call that was centred around an FSTP mechanism in the 2024 Mission calls. This FSTP provision could be made mandatory in some/most/all of the remaining work programmes for Phase 2 of the Mission, to provide a number of small grants (of perhaps €5000 - €20 000, representing 5%-10% of the total call value) for different activities depending on the project's focus. This would give small groups, communities, citizen science initiatives, *etc.*, a reason to consistently engage with the Mission on a yearly basis, investigate what the projects are, who is providing funding, what is the Mission doing, and overall to see its benefit via small scale funding.

4.2 Stakeholder engagement recommendations

Effective stakeholder (SH) engagement is a cornerstone of the Mission Ocean and Waters, requiring inclusive, collaborative, and sustained action across diverse sectors and communities. Drawing on the insights from Prep4Blue and building towards the second phase of the Mission, several critical lessons and forward-looking recommendations have emerged (Figure 10):

1. **Developing an Integrated Stakeholder Engagement Strategy:** The first phase of the Mission, supported by multiple CSAs, highlighted the richness but also the fragmentation of stakeholder engagement approaches. While each CSA adopted its own strategy, a more unified and comprehensive strategy remains needed. A consolidated Mission-wide Stakeholder Engagement Strategy could build on CSA experiences, promote coherence, and guide future R&I projects.

2. **Improving Application of Engagement Methods (SHEM):** Prep4Blue performed ex-ante analyses of stakeholder engagement methods, which were collected and systematised in WaveLinks. However, their effectiveness should now be validated with concrete application cases from Mission-funded projects, such as the Pilot Stakeholder Assemblies. A robust mechanism for tracking, analyzing, and sharing real-world engagement outcomes should be developed in phase two.
3. **Segmenting the Mission Stakeholder Ecosystem:** One of the key challenges was the complexity and scale of the stakeholder ecosystem. Achieving goal-oriented and efficient engagement requires refined segmentation frameworks that can map stakeholder categories, roles, and influence levels more precisely—supporting targeted outreach and reducing fragmentation.
4. **Fostering Horizontal Coordination Across Lighthouses:** Silos between the Lighthouses’ stakeholder ecosystems could hinder synergies. Establishing cross-cutting “horizontal connectors” and EU-level coordination mechanisms would enhance collaboration, avoid duplication, and build a shared sense of mission across sea basins.
5. **Customized Communication Strategies:** Adapting messaging and formats to the needs and expectations of different stakeholder groups improves relevance, clarity, and engagement impact.
6. **Strengthening Ocean Literacy in Europe:** Promoting awareness and understanding of ocean and water issues—especially through education, public outreach, and citizen science—empowers citizens and strengthens societal support for Mission goals.
7. **Fostering Public-Private-Research Collaboration:** Effective engagement must bridge academia, industry, civil society, and policymakers. Mechanisms to facilitate transdisciplinary collaboration, co-creation, and joint ownership of results are essential.
8. **Early Involvement of Stakeholders:** Engaging stakeholders from the design phase increases legitimacy and relevance. Early engagement enhances shared responsibility, builds trust, and can shape project priorities more effectively.
9. **Providing Tangible Incentives:** Incentives—monetary or otherwise—motivate participation and help maintain long-term stakeholder commitment.
10. **Supporting Grassroots Initiatives:** Funding and technical support for local and community-led actions ensures inclusive engagement and reinforces ownership at the territorial level.
11. **Moving Towards Collaborative Governance Models:** Empowering stakeholders through participatory and deliberative mechanisms represents a shift from top-down to shared governance—fostering democratic legitimacy and long-term resilience.
12. **Promoting Long-Term Engagement Structures:** Sustainable impact requires continuous feedback loops, long-term relationships, and stakeholder representation in decision-making bodies.
13. **Enhancing Visibility and Accessibility of Support Services:** Despite the creation of tools such as the Prep4Blue Helpdesk, usage remained low. Future services must be more widely promoted, user-oriented, and embedded in stakeholder workflows to ensure uptake and relevance.

SH engagement

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Figure 10. Key recommendations by Prep4Blue on Stakeholder Engagement in Mission Ocean & Waters

4.3 Communication recommendations

Clear, inclusive, and coordinated communication is essential to the success of the Mission Ocean and Waters. It plays a key role in raising awareness, supporting stakeholder engagement, and ensuring that the Mission's goals and activities are understood and embraced across diverse sectors and communities. To this end, the following recommendations focus on enhancing internal communication processes, improving access to information, and strengthening the visibility and impact of scientific and public outreach. Particular attention is given to developing communication approaches that are responsive to the needs of different audiences, from policymakers and researchers to civil society organisations and local communities.

4.3.1 Mission Communication Activities

To strengthen internal communication within the Mission Ocean and Waters framework and enhance stakeholder engagement, the following recommendations (Table 5). aim to improve information flow, accessibility, and compliance across key stakeholder groups:

1. **Centralize Information and Opportunities**

Target Stakeholders: Policy-makers and Funding Organisations

To improve access to updates, opportunities, and engagement activities, it is recommended to establish a unified platform that consolidates information from various EU Mission Ocean and Waters projects. This central hub will reduce fragmentation, allowing stakeholders and citizens to easily navigate and retrieve relevant content without the need to consult multiple sources.

2. Consolidate Information on Funding Opportunities

Target Stakeholders: Citizens, Civil Society Organisations (CSOs), and Sectoral Stakeholders

A centralized platform dedicated to aggregating funding opportunities is proposed to simplify the search process and increase visibility of available resources. By streamlining access to funding information from different projects, stakeholders can engage more effectively with the Mission’s financial instruments.

3. Clarify Social Media Responsibilities and Compliance

Target Stakeholders: Policy-makers and Funding Organisations

It is essential to clearly define roles and responsibilities for managing Mission-related social media channels. This includes ensuring alignment with EU regulations and proactively addressing potential legal ambiguities. A structured governance model will support a consistent, compliant, and professional digital presence.

Table 5. Recommendations on Stakeholder engagement related to Mission internal communication activities

(Source: Prep4blue [D6.5](#) - Pathways to develop capacity/skills needs to achieve the Mission targets by 2030)

Group	Recommendation	Stakeholders			Description
		R&I	Policy-makers & Funding organisations	Citizens CSOs & Sectoral Stakeholders	
 Mission Internal Communication	Centralize information and opportunities		✓		Establish a unified platform that consolidates information from the 60 mission Ocean and Waters projects, making it easier for citizens and stakeholders to access updates, funding opportunities, and engagement activities without navigating multiple websites. Skills: Web developer skills, SEO
	Consolidate information on funding opportunities		✓		Create a centralized platform that aggregates funding opportunities from various projects, simplifying access for stakeholders and reducing the need to navigate multiple sources. Skills: Web developer skills, SEO
	Clarify social media responsibilities and compliance		✓		Clearly define roles and responsibilities for managing social media channels, ensuring compliance with EU regulations. Address any legal ambiguities proactively to maintain a consistent and effective online presence. Skills: Project management

4.3.2 Marine Science Communication activities

To support impactful communication of science related to the Mission Ocean and Waters, the following (Table 6) recommendations have been developed to foster effective outreach, raise public awareness, and ensure inclusivity in how scientific progress is shared with various stakeholders.

1. Establish Dedicated Mixed Teams to Manage Communication for Specific Initiatives

Target Stakeholders: R&I actors, Policy-makers and Funding Organisations, Citizens/CSOs & Sectoral Stakeholders.

The creation of dedicated communication groups is recommended. These teams should include project partners and representatives from the European Commission. Equipped with clear guidelines, consistent terminology, and defined key messages, such teams will coordinate social media and outreach activities in alignment with the broader institutional communication strategy.

2. Plan and Execute High-Impact Public Engagement Events

Target Stakeholders: *R&I actors, Policy-makers and Funding Organisations*

To extend engagement beyond the immediate scientific and policy communities, significant resources and time should be allocated to planning well-promoted public events. These events should be designed to genuinely engage the public and foster broader participation and awareness.

3. Develop Diverse Narratives

Target Stakeholders: *R&I actors, Policy-makers and Funding Organisations, Citizens/CSOs & Sectoral Stakeholders*

Diverse narratives tailored to different cultural and ethnic groups should be crafted to improve relevance, resonance, and inclusivity. This strategy enables communication to reach and engage marginalised or less represented communities more effectively.

4. Develop Engaging Multimedia Content

Target Stakeholders: *R&I actors, Policy-makers and Funding Organisations, Citizens/CSOs & Sectoral Stakeholders*

Documentaries and videos showcasing Mission activities—especially across the four Lighthouse areas—should be produced. These materials should reflect the diversity of challenges and communities involved, and be made accessible through subtitles and multiple languages. This storytelling approach can inspire, inform, and mobilise a wider audience around the Mission’s goals.

Table 6. Recommendations on Stakeholder engagement related to Marine Science Communication activities
(Source: Prep4blue D6.5 - Pathways to develop capacity/skills needs to achieve the Mission targets by 2030)

Group	Recommendation	Stakeholders			Description
		R&I	Policy-makers & Funding organisations	Citizens CSOs & Sectoral Stakeholders	
 Marine Science Communication (MSC)	Establish dedicated mixed teams to manage communication for specific initiatives like the Mission Ocean and Waters.	✓	✓	✓	Dedicated communication groups that include project partners and representatives from the EC. These teams should be supported by clear guidelines, key messages, and consistent terminology tailored for social media use, to ensure coherent and effective outreach within the broader institutional communication framework. Skills: communication, social media knowledge
	Plan and execute high-impact public engagement events	✓	✓		Allocate sufficient resources and time to organize events that genuinely engage the public and extend beyond the immediate project community. Large-scale, well-promoted events can significantly raise awareness and foster broader participation. Skills: organizational skills, effective communication, financial skills, logistics
	Develop diverse narratives	✓	✓		Crafting multiple narratives tailored to various cultural and ethnic groups ensures broader reach and resonance, particularly among marginalized communities. Skills: cultural awareness, communication
	Develop engaging multimedia content			✓	Produce documentaries and videos showcasing mission activities, covering the four Lighthouses because they address different problems and show cultural diversity, and make them available in multiple languages with subtitles. This approach can inspire and inform a broader audience about the mission's objectives and progress. Skills: videomaking, storytelling, project management

5 Conclusions

Prep4Blue has provided a comprehensive set of resources and tested approaches to support effective public engagement in the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters.” Its dual focus on citizens and stakeholders enabled the development of practical methods that can be taken up by Mission-funded projects and initiatives across Europe.

Prep4Blue’s outputs have shown that:

- Citizens can play a key role in the co-design and implementation of Mission-related activities, especially through networks such as citizen science initiatives and ocean literacy organisations.
- Stakeholders, including local authorities, research institutions, businesses, and NGOs, require targeted support to collaborate effectively across sectors and regions. Prep4Blue delivered this through guidelines, digital tools, training, and knowledge exchange.

While Prep4Blue did not carry out large-scale engagement directly, it equipped future Mission actors—such as R&I projects and coordination initiatives—with the frameworks and support structures to do so. The project also fostered collaboration among CSAs and provided tested formats for participatory governance.

Looking ahead, the outputs of Prep4Blue are expected to continue supporting the Mission’s progress by enabling inclusive, well-structured, and locally relevant engagement strategies. As the Mission moves into its next phase, these contributions will be essential to ensuring broad ownership, trust, and long-term success in restoring our ocean and waters.